

Utilization of treatment services among Filipino men in uniform with sexual dysfunctions: Implications for a technology-based treatment delivery system

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Abstract

Sexual dysfunctions are considered a taboo and a stigmatizing topic among Men in Uniform (MIU), but the said dysfunctions remain a very serious concern among the group, and thus need to be explored so that an appropriate treatment delivery system can be developed for them. Using in-depth interviews, this study examined perceptions of sexual dysfunction and utilization of treatment services among Filipino MIU with a sexual dysfunction. Results revealed that the MIU perceived their sexual dysfunction to have decreased their sense and feeling of masculinity and to have significantly negatively affected their sexual relationships. Moreover, the MIU were found to have availed of treatment services from the public (i.e., military hospital) as well as from the private sector. Although many MIU were attracted by the cost-free services offered at the public hospital, the MIU in general preferred receiving treatment at private facilities, because the latter were perceived as better in safeguarding the privacy and anonymity of the patient. However, overall, the MIU were not open in consulting let alone in receiving treatment from health providers due to the prevailing social stigma and discrimination against men with a sexual dysfunction. As a result, many were found to have resorted to scouring various websites in search for a treatment. These findings suggest that a new approach is needed to help more Filipino MIU having sexual dysfunction to seek and receive treatment. A technology-based treatment delivery system that is readily accessible, discreet, and confidential is imperative.

Keywords: *Sexual dysfunction; Men in uniform; Treatment; Technology-based treatment delivery system; Health technology; Filipino men.*

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Introduction

In this current era where there is a standard call for healthcare access and services to encompass all sectors of society, it is very important to look at each sector and check whether their healthcare needs are met and served. The Reproductive Health Approach concept was first initiated during the International Conference on Population and Development (ICPD) with strong distinction that every detail and levels of reproductive and sexual health should be equally given to both sexes. It was also stressed that men should be included as a target population to have role on responsible parenthood, prevention of sexually transmitted infections (STI), and coping and management of sexual dysfunctions according to Marcell et al. (2011).

However, one of the most underserved sectors in health is the male population in general most especially regarding reproductive health treatment services. Pearson (2003) stated that reproductive and sexual health sectors are usually tasked to provide services to women only (e.g., providing contraceptives, performance of pregnancy tests, STI testing), as experts dictate that

females are the ones at risk of conception; thus, the health sector believes that they have greater need of services. This leads into the underutilization of reproductive and sexual health services among men. Ho et al. (2011) attributed the underutilization to the male populations' fear of societal inhibition and loss of their attributed strong masculine role that leads to their non-consult and underutilization.

Moreover, the lack of available reproductive and sexual health services for targeting men tend to promote the development of poor health seeking behaviors such as non-disclosure and non-seeking of professional help regarding their sexual problems. The act of self-medication has been observed in men who experienced apprehension on utilizing treatment for sexual health problems that includes alcohol consumption, consumption of herbal medicines, and usage of sexual apparatuses. One important dimension of male sexuality is sexual dysfunction. These identified dysfunctions do not only manifest physical impairments but also strongly contribute to the psychosocial aspect of health and quality of life. Transcending beyond the biomedical model of health, sexual dysfunctions also affect the socioeconomic, cultural, and emotional dimensions of the afflicted. Sexual dysfunction is on the topmost prevalent psychological disorders affecting both sexes according to Spector and Carey (1990). Globally, studies such as the study of Nicolosi et al. (2004) with a sample size of 27,500 males collected from 29 countries revealed that as per region basis, Premature Ejaculation (PE) emerged as the most prevalent sexual dysfunction in the world followed by Erectile Dysfunction. Several studies have correlated sexual dysfunction with poor Quality of Life (QoL) such as a study of Rosen et al. (2004). These sexual dysfunctions have great impact on the sexual well-being of the afflicted man.

Military sexual health has been a vaguely studied topic in research. Studies made on the military health have focused largely on posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD), major depression, generalized anxiety, and traumatic brain injuries (TBI) caused by warfare. These are called "invisible wounds of war." However, men in uniform also suffer sexual dysfunctions which are bothersome and a taboo topic. Although the military is a young and vigorous force, service members and veterans (military personnel) may experience several hidden injuries that may influence their quality of life (QoL) which importantly includes sexual functioning (Wilcox et al., 2014).

Utilization of treatment services among men in uniform with sexual dysfunction

Positive sexual health is defined as attaining the capacity to engage in meaningful mutual intimate relationships that would promote satisfaction. However, there are conditions that would affect the state of one's sexual functioning and health. Prevalence of sexual dysfunction was explored through the study of Feldman (1994) in which the dysfunction was classified into different categories. The largest category was moderate dysfunction defined as can assume erection but becomes flaccid after several minutes of penetrative sexual activity at 25.2% prevalence, followed by minimal dysfunction defined as full assumption of erection and the capacity to do penetrative sexual activity however has difficulty to attain another erection at 17.2% prevalence, and the smallest was complete dysfunction at 9.6% prevalence.

Sexual dysfunction continues to be under-detected in sexual health centers in the military and psychosexual services are not prioritized as stated by Ho et al. (2011) and Nicolosi et al. (2005). It is estimated that globally, sixty-three (63%) of the military men have sexual dysfunction with vast causes such as co-morbidities and sexual apprehension, adding to specified barriers are

male poor health seeking behaviors, stigmatization of medical care, most especially in terms of reproductive or sexual health. Solstad (1993) estimated that approximately there is 25% of military men who have sought consult for sexual dysfunctions. It was estimated that 8% of MIU seek for medical help for undiagnosed dysfunctions. It was also reported that approximately 40% of MIU has or is currently experiencing one type of sexual dysfunction of which these MIU are afraid and uninterested to utilize reproductive health services. MIU attributed these dysfunctions to aging (7%) and a part of a specific disorder or disease (2%). With these statistics only 5% of MIU surveyed planned to consult a doctor or a sexual therapist.

Sexual dysfunction leads to severe impairment of one's QoL that leads to decreased satisfaction and levels of happiness. Despite of these, Wilcox et al. (2014) noted that only a small number of MIU have fully submitted to treatment. Non-seeking treatment was attributed to societal factors such as disruption of societal image and what other people may think. Several studies also pointed that the military population has one of the lowest treatment seeking rates marked with high treatment attrition rates for sexual health treatment with numbers ranging of 17% successful treatment and 73% attrition rate. It was also noted that stigma was the most important issue in acquisition and maintenance of treatment. Due to the attached stigma on treatment seeking, aggravation and increased severity of reported symptoms usually occur.

Zinzow and Thompson (2015) further investigated treatment practices in the military. Results show that 25% of MIU dropped out of sexual problem treatment even before completion. Self-reliance was defined as an especially prominent barrier in military samples, due to the fact that military culture encourages retaining mental toughness and prioritizing the unit mission over individual needs (Zinzow & Thompson, 2015). Similar results were noted in the study of Landes et al. (2013) which stated that many of the military men wanted to seek for sexual health treatment if there would be private one-on-one consultation and counseling. Men are not at ease like in women during complete clinical evaluation and examination pertaining to sexual and reproductive health. Counseling and treatment with the presence of other people would exacerbate their inhibition to seek treatment. It was emphasized that military men like and constantly requested for discreet one-on-one counseling of their sexual health problems. Sornberger (2015) suggested that sexual dysfunction could occur for many reasons, including a malfunction of equipment, low desire, or the vulnerability of being unable to see or do something. Barriers to treatment that were discussed included accessibility to treatment, finding a provider that understands the scenario, difficulty starting the conversation, and difficulty of the provider asking the questions, among others.

However, despite the presence of a true dysfunction, MIU results to seeking alternative methods to alleviate sexual dysfunction and retain their societal gender role. Alternative treatment methods for sexual dysfunction includes consumption of aphrodisiac herbs such as the study of Malviya et al. (2011) where traditional herbs were only adjuvant to sexual health treatment. Lingam massage was also seen as an alternative to treatment and counseling for sexual dysfunction. Monido (2013) stated that this type of massage aims to provide benefits to male sexual dysfunction sufferers which is to correct energy imbalances, prevent prostate cancer, and control male orgasm. "Sex toys" was also seen as an alternative to treatment. In the study of Katz et al. (2011), penile suction and vacuums tend to imitate the actual normal erectile state and thus bring back innate sense of solid masculine functionality.

Non-utilization and low treatment rates of MIU was connected to several factors. Sexual dysfunction was seen to be a threat to their masculinity and considered to be as "broken

masculinity.” MIU would remain discrete regarding their sexual health condition attributed with the fear of societal loss of control and rejection. This in turn leads to non-seeking treatment or seeking non-prescriptive alternative treatments.

There are studies indicating that male military personnel who have or had experienced sexual dysfunction are often presented with difficulties that prevent their utilization of sexual and reproductive health services. Masculine pride, shame and embarrassment, and strong stigmatization were raised as the most important barriers to utilization of reproductive health service among military men. Military men did not feel comfortable approaching a reproductive health center, as they believed that sexual health is a matter between females, and they are rather preoccupied in finding ways to improve their sexual performance than consulting a sexual health center.

According to Brotto et al. (2016), MIU would rather consult the world wide web or the internet to search for ways to improve sexual performance and address sexual dysfunction, and it keeps a certain amount of intimacy amongst them. Although the internet cannot replace face-to-face consultation, it was noted that the use of the computer provided the room for confidentiality and anonymity thus will not result to fear of embarrassment and prejudice. This will result in unhindered and effective reproductive health treatment.

Benefits from utilization of treatment services for sexual dysfunction

Utilization of treatment services for sexual dysfunction among MIU brings significant improvement at the personal, relational, and occupational levels. With the use of effective treatment schemes for sexual dysfunction, the importance of “a return to manhood” can therefore not be underestimated in generating a sense of wellbeing and confidence, likewise it is critical for a man to be able to fulfill his partner's sexual needs (Tomlinson & Wright, 2004). In the study of Thangadurai et al. (2014), establishing a rapport with the patient, communicating with them about sexuality respectfully and without judgment, acknowledging their distress, getting their perspective, educating them about the nature of their illness, and addressing any misconceptions or anxieties they may have, are all essential to the successful management of sexual dysfunction. In the same note, Dean et al. (2006) elaborated that improvement in each partner’s satisfaction reinforce the positive effects of successful treatment on and on the intimacy of their intimate relationships. As Dean et al. (2006) emphasized successful treatment of sexual dysfunctions may improve men’s sexual self-confidence, self-esteem and psychological wellbeing as the perception of self-improvement becomes a factor in reliving the machismo spirit of a man.

The ultimate benefit that they had after utilization of treatment services is the improvement of their sex life. This entails that MIU had improved marital relationships and marital satisfaction after their use of treatment services for their sexual dysfunction. The high rate of patient dissatisfaction and dropout with these therapies may be due primarily to the medical treatments' limited ability to address the larger individual psychological and relational issues that are implicated in many cases of sexual dysfunction (McCabe & Matic, 2008). Furthermore, Dunn (2004) quoted, “*When a couple may be about to resume an intimate, romantic relationship after a prolonged absence from sexual activity as brought about by sexual dysfunctions, having the participation of both partners is invaluable.*” Therefore, Dunn (2004) suggested that involving men’s partners in couple counseling shall be instituted to address concerns that remains unaddressed by current medical interventions.

Sexual dysfunction has also been attributed to difficulties in performing occupational tasks in the military; several narratives of MIU narrated that utilization of treatment service has improved their mood at work, improved their performance of assigned tasks, and increased their productivity. Sexual activity seems to encourage the production of opioids and dopamine, which reinforce positive behavior and could raise overall wellbeing as stated by Leavitt (2019). In the same study, it was also pointed that in contrast with individuals who do not follow sexual activity, treatment seeking leads employees to view their work time through the positive lens of sex-induced positive emotional states. Sexual behavior does in fact positively influence both job satisfaction and job engagement the following day as a function of increased positive effect (Leavitt, 2019).

Challenges on utilization of treatment services for sexual dysfunction

The study of reproductive health treatment service among men in general has strictly focused on prevention of sexually transmitted infections (STI) and HIV-AIDS; likewise, majority of the focus has also been on the role of males on RH choices of their female partners. Opposition to male involvement in reproductive health services utilization especially for sexual dysfunctions often comes from men themselves. Men's unwillingness to alter their reproductive health behaviors, their feelings of embarrassment, and their notion that reproductive health should keep a female-focused area were also mentioned (Walston, 2005).

Men participating in RH therapies have a number of challenges, including overcoming emotions of shame and embarrassment as well as addressing cultural norms surrounding seeking medical attention. First, men are less likely than women to request a diagnosis, treatment, or therapy (Walston, 2005). Another concern is that men were more likely to turn to private practitioners than to traditional healers or other public health care providers. Private practitioners are seen to be more accessible, more time flexible, and more accommodating than public service providers. The public health system suffers from limited staff and poor capacity. Many health facilities, especially those in rural areas, operate during unfavorable hours and have inadequate staffing and equipment. Increasing male involvement aimed at the public health system may put additional demand on already limited resources without addressing underutilization, the system's main issue.

Another challenge in reproductive health service utilization is men's stringent time considerations. Men in uniform are generally time crunched. MIU will have usually perceived utilization of RH service as "loss of income through lost work time." The utilization of public health services is influenced by a number of critical factors, including accessibility, affordability, social and cultural barriers, lack of knowledge, and treatment effectiveness as perceived (Tuot et al., 2016).

Another significant barrier to SHC utilization was care-related constraints associated to masculinity. Participants consistently connected unwillingness to seek such care with characteristics of what a guy means in all groups. Men occasionally used words like "macho," "male ego," or "being a guy" to explicitly link their behavior to being a man. In other instances, they talked about stereotypically masculine traits without mentioning them by name. For instance, participants frequently brought up the need to act in a way that invoked strength, emotions of invulnerability to weakness and disease, and the ability to manage on one's own without asking for assistance from others when discussing why males do not seek SHC (Kalmuss & Austrian, 2010).

In the interview transcript of Kalmuss and Austrian (2010), the idea that having a sexual dysfunction stigmatized a man, made people think less of him, and made it more difficult for him to find partners ready to have sex with him, was a big fear-related issue that came back to concepts of masculinity. Males in all groups linked this image to their reluctance to be around sexual health facilities.

The study describes the utilization of treatment services as well as the benefits derived, and challenges experienced among selected Filipino men in uniform (MIU) with sexual dysfunction. Specifically, this study answers the following research questions:

1. How do they utilize the treatment services for sexual dysfunctions?
2. How does their utilization of treatment services vary according to their perceptions about reproductive health and sexual dysfunctions?
3. What benefits do they derive from the utilization of treatment services for sexual dysfunction?
4. What challenges do they encounter in their utilization of treatment services for sexual dysfunction?

Methods

This study utilized a qualitative-descriptive research design with non-probability sampling technique. It included key informant interviews of men in uniform. Also, a face-to-face interview was used as a research method in this. The population of this study involved men in uniform stationed in a province in Southern Luzon, Philippines. This study involved 15 key informants from different armed forces units as sample. Key informants are chosen through a purposive-convenient sampling, although referral sampling was also considered.

The voice-recorded in-depth conversations were transcribed, and the information acquired was arranged in accordance with the research issues each one addressed. To evaluate the data, content analysis was applied to the interview transcriptions. Given the similarities and contrasts among the topics, the information was examined and presented.

Results

Men in uniform reported experienced sexual dysfunction. The informants stated that they experience lack of libido or sexual desire which was attributed to their heavy workload and training.

*Utilization of treatment services for sexual dysfunction***Table 1.** Utilization of treatment services

Themes	Subthemes	Mentioned Examples
Service Sources	Public Sources	Military Doctors and Hospital Infantry Clinics
	Private Sources	Private Doctors Private Hospitals Private Counselors Product Demonstrations
	Other Sources	Peers Self-searched treatment TV advertisements Internet / Online sources
Service Type	Physical Services	Prescription / Medication Surgical Referral Herbal Supplements and Concoctions Enhancing Gels
	Psychological Services	Discreet Counseling Sessions

MIU utilize treatment services from different available sources. Public sources which are provided by military or government centers, private sources or centers operated by private corporations and other sources such as peers, the internet, and mass media. Private sources were more preferred by MIU covering private medical doctors, family doctors, and private counselors among others. One reason for this is because of hesitation of talking to a military doctor regarding treatment services. Informants also stated that it is shameful to seek treatment inside the military base because of the fear of disclosure of condition and treatment seeking. As an informant stated, *“They will tend to seek private sources. They will be hesitant to seek treatment at the base, because of disclosure of him having sexual dysfunction among other members of the force.”*

MIU utilize both physical and psychological type of treatment services for sexual dysfunction. MIU believe that prescription medicines are the best solution to any sexual dysfunction, and it is accessible upon consultation and prescription of a medical doctor. Informants also further suggested that medicines are still the preferred treatment of military men because it is not affected by ego. One middle aged informant stated, *“Mostly it will be medicine especially among those who are sexually active. Counselling is not common in the armed forces because of ego. I’m more into medication; it’s the best. I usually buy outside or through the internet.”*

MIU also expressed the importance of counseling in the management of sexual dysfunction. MIU narrated that they are experiencing a lot of stressful and traumatic events which could add to the severity of their dysfunction. MIU also believed that it is beneficial to have someone to talk to regarding problems brought about by sexual dysfunction. One MIU said that, *“It is very important to have counseling for those who lack sexual stamina because of work. It is good to have someone to talk to regarding your dysfunction. But it depends, for those who are having erection problems, maybe it could be attributed to lack of physical activity which could be counseled also effectively.”*

In a similar note, majority of the MIU informants emphasized that a member of the armed forces will still seek treatment but in a discreet manner and avoiding disclosure of usage of treatment services among peers in the military and should be there means to avail treatment without disclosure is of advantage. One informant stated, *“Definitely they would seek treatment, but it*

would have to be discreet and not disclosed. Military men tend to be discreet on those things, as they would not want their colleagues to know that they have a dysfunction. It will be huge source of jokes and ridicule.”

Benefits of utilization of treatment services

Table 2. Benefits of utilization of treatment services

Themes	Subthemes	Mentioned Examples
Personal Based Benefits	Trustworthy Treatment Economical Psychological Educational	Assured effectivity Free to avail and use Improved self-esteem Proper education for caring of male sexual health problems
Relational Based Benefits	Sexual and Marital Satisfaction	Improved sex life Better conception of wife More aggressive actions towards intimate act
Occupational Based Benefits	Better Productivity	Improved mood at work Improved focus and stamina in performing work tasks

MIU mentioned that utilizing treatment services improved their sexual function which in turn also improves their relationship with their intimate partner. Furthermore, informants revealed that there are significant benefits brought about by utilizing treatment. One MIU quoted, *“Of course, your performance will improve, and you will gain increased self-esteem. Your wife will be happy, and your performance at work will improve.”*

Men in uniform also noted personal benefits with utilizing treatment services. It was noted that treatment services utilization is usually seen as availing an effective and trustworthy treatment. MIU further explained that availing treatment services is more economical than self-medication and long-term complication treatment. One informant stated, *“Beside the fact that it is free, we are surer that it is more effective, like in my case I have a sexual dysfunction. I’m sure it would really help, because if you aim to be married and have kids in the future, you must make sure that you take care of your own reproductive organs. So we will stick to what is effective, trustworthy, and economical.”*

MIU also highlighted the unmatched effectiveness of treatment utilization than other means of treatment service such as traditional services and self-medication. One later aged informant mentioned, *“Of course, your problem will be treated than traditional healers which of no certainty. If you seek for treatment center’s advice and treatment, you will be healed 99% of the time.”*

MIU also identified benefits brought by utilization of treatment in their work conditions or occupational benefits. MIU mentioned that utilizing treatment services leads to improved mood at work and improved focus and stamina in performing work tasks. A navy captain with vast knowledge regarding his condition quoted, *“Sexual dysfunctions are manageable and reversible conditions. Once diagnosed, men will be treated to improve their function in the military to their assigned tasks and also with their family.”*

Challenges as to utilization of treatment services

MIU both identified personal and relational challenges as the most encountered challenges in the utilization of treatment services. According to the MIU, personal challenges such as non-disclosure of diagnosis and treatment seeking and associated decrease in manhood were commonly encountered after treatment utilization. Moreover, the informants explained that there would be hesitation to seek treatment due to a perceived decrease in manhood mandated by societal views of masculinity.

Table 3. Challenges of treatment service utilization

Themes	Mentioned Examples
Personal Based Challenges	Utilization decreases manhood Utilization leads to non-disclosure of diagnosis and treatment Avoids utilization due to lack of confidence to seek treatment and to know diagnosis Utilization results to lack of self-esteem Utilization leads to hurt ego Utilization against religious beliefs and values
Relational Based Challenges	Judgment of peers – Being ridiculed by peers Avoidance by peers Treatment is a taboo according to peers Stereotypes from peers
Occupational Based Challenges	Lack of time due to extended schedules Heavy workload Stressful work conditions Remote deployment
Facility Based Challenges	Lack of equipment, medicines, and supplies in military treatment centers Lack of specialized doctors in military treatment centers Judgment of military doctors upon seeking treatments No facility in remote deployment areas Proximity of treatment service providers

One informant stated, *“Maybe they would be hesitant to seek treatment because it may decrease their self-esteem because of their dysfunction. They would be hesitant because of their masculinity. It is very important for us to be masculine always.”*

The informants also elaborated the strong military culture that hinder disclosure of sexual dysfunction and treatment utilization among peers. The informants also mentioned that there will be a significant blow as to masculinity upon disclosure of the presence of sexual dysfunction and seeking treatment services. One middle aged informant quoted, *“Of course you are a uniformed personnel. You look very masculine, and then people will find out that you cannot have an erection. It would be a blow to your masculinity and your personality. It will be such a shame.”*

MIU likewise equally mentioned society-imposed challenges as one of the major challenges in utilizing treatment services for sexual dysfunctions. Being judged and ridiculed by peers was one of the challenges raised by MIU. One informant cited a scenario where he personally experienced being judged for seeking treatment for sexual dysfunction due to his early age, *“They have judged me. They told me, ‘You are so young to have a problem like that and seek treatment,’ but I think they would understand they would also get old and will have their own problem.”*

Likewise, it was also noted that armed personnel upon disclosure of dysfunction and treatment utilization would be equated into teasing, ridicule, and being tagged as a weakling, not fit for the profession and being effeminate. One informant stated, *“It is a personal issue, as*

uniformed personnel we always tease each other, so you will be afraid to be teased if you have a problem, they better hide it to themselves. If you cannot function you are a weakling, they will look different at you and your self-esteem and ego will also go down. Some will mention that you better just be a girl or be gay to have some sex.”

MIU also identified challenges brought about by their line of work. Majority of them mentioned that their existing duty schedules cause the lack of time to utilize treatment services for their sexual dysfunction and would hope that there will be other ways to seek for help. One informant said, “*Buong oras mo sa trabaho, paano ka pa makakapagpapagamot? Swerte ka kung may doctor na pupunta o may pribado na bukas ng Sabado. Sana kung meron lang sa kompyuter na lang para kahit anong oras [You're working all the time; how else can you get treatment? You're lucky if there is a doctor or there are Saturday working hours. I wish there were online (consultations) at any time].”*

Discussion

MIU expressed that they experience lack of sexual desire as brought about by rigid training and overloaded workload and schedules. This narrative is further explained by Sangi-Haghpeykar et al. (2009) where male trainees who were exposed to important levels of stress and prolonged work hours had significant impact on their sexual desire whereas other domains of sexual well-being (erection and ejaculation) were affected moderately. Likewise, Sexual dysfunction is frequently caused by stress at work, conflict with coworkers, financial hardships, and physical effort. All of these could hinder a man from experiencing the highest level of sexual fulfillment (Kalra, 2010).

Since most MIU's experiences lack of sexual desire, they would seek for counseling sessions to be able to alleviate their perceived effect of sexual dysfunction as to quality of life namely triggered irritability and decreased sense of masculinity. Likewise, MIU also utilize these services to improve their focus at work and their work performance. The use of psychological treatment services also improves their married life status thus improving their relational well-being. Interestingly, a previous study confirmed that counseling sessions and other attachment-building therapies may be helpful for treating current sexual dysfunction as well as for improving the overall relationships and lowering the risk of future intimacy problems (Bennett et al., 2012). A model as proposed by Kalra (2010) called the “Karnal Model” for male sexual dysfunction counseling involves counseling offered by one same-sex therapist. In our situation, this model approach is typically more productive, less embarrassing, and socially acceptable than a combined session with therapists. It is a comprehensive approach to address all determinants of sexual dysfunction.

Problems as to physical dysfunction such as difficulty to attain and sustain erection and flaccid penis are addressed by physical services offered by treatment centers which include provision of prescription medications as most stated by the MIU except for one instance of complaints of painful intercourse due to a prostate problem which would have to be referred and be addressed by a private treatment center.

Majority of the physical complaints of men as to sexual dysfunction could be addressed by modern medical treatments available in the market. In the study of Van Kampen et al. (2003), medications together with perineal and relaxation exercises provided by physical therapists could significantly improve sexual dysfunction complaints on men. There are also other studies

indicating other treatment protocols for sexual dysfunction. In another study performed by Monido (2013), it was found out that lingam massage was beneficial into bringing back erections, sexual sensations, and sexual vigor the act itself was considered be an act of passive sex.

MIU expressed that these services are available to both public and private sources with emphasis that they prefer public service availment due to its accessibility and it is free of charge. However, for the sense of privacy, security of non-disclosure and efficacy of treatment, MIU opts to seek treatment in private treatment service providers. In the study of Thangadurai et al. (2014), men with sexual difficulties are more likely to seek out healing and cure elsewhere, rendering them more exposed to exploitation, due to a lack of emphasis and experience in basic and secondary care, particularly in public treatment facilities. Basu (2012) performed a systematic review of treatment utilization in public and private settings. While private sector clinicians reported being prompter and accommodating to patients, they also frequently violated medical norms of practice and had worse patient outcomes; unnecessary testing and treatment was also noted at this setting. Equipment, drugs, and skilled healthcare personnel were more scarcely available for public sector services.

Utilization of treatment services for sexual dysfunction among MIU brings significant improvement at the personal, relational, and occupational levels. At the personal level, emerging themes included the provision of effective treatment for sexual dysfunction. With the use of effective treatment schemes for sexual dysfunction, the significance of returning to manhood in creating a sense of wellbeing and confidence cannot be understated (Tomlinson & Wright, 2004).

Another theme that emerged from the narratives at the personal level is improvement of self-esteem in which they have increased self-worth and betterment of mood and emotions as to their self. Majority of the MIU have expressed that the ultimate benefit that they had after utilization of treatment services is the improvement of their sex life. This entails that MIU had improved sexual performance, improved marital relationships, and marital satisfaction after their use of treatment services for their sexual dysfunction.

While there are benefits derived from the utilization of treatment service for sexual dysfunction, there also present challenges encountered by MIU upon their treatment service utilization. The challenges and issues include personal, relational, occupational, and facility-based challenges. MIU mostly mentioned that relational and personal issues are their most encountered issues. As to the personal subtheme, MIU perceived that when they utilize treatment services for their sexual dysfunction, they feel emasculated or their sense of manhood decreases. Shabsigh et al. (2004) stated that the conflict between the conventional masculine roles of authority, self-reliance, and emotional control causes men to be reluctant to use health care. To explain further, a study by Evans et al. (2011) in general concluded that gender ideologies restrict men more than they do women, subjecting them to harsher criticism and shame if they deviate toward unmanly or feminine behaviors and fail to uphold or reject idealized conceptions of masculinity.

In a MIU narrative, it was stated that those who suffer sexual dysfunction would still seek treatment but in a discreet manner, moreover, MIU also believe in the non-disclosure of their current dysfunctional state and treatment utilization. The narratives of MIU were further confirmed by the study of Gray (2000) where men seriously consider disclosure of diagnosis and treatment seeking because in its pure nature, sexual dysfunction is stigmatizing. Some perceive it as “socially dangerous” and imbibing negative judgments thus leading to lesser levels of willingness to disclose. This confirms that most men would like their status and treatment seeking hidden and discreet.

It is important to note that as to social relationships, the biggest challenge for MIU to seek and utilize treatment is the judgment or attached stigma and ridicule from their peers in the military. Most of the MIU narrated that upon learning of their dysfunction status, they have first thought of the judgment that they will face from their peers in the military service. It was observed that only a small percentage of soldiers who experience sexual health issues seek professional assistance, which has been linked to organizational restrictions and stigma. As Kim et al. (2011) emphasized, stigma can be thought of as a "mark" that distinguishes one person from another and associates them with bad traits. Public ideas, prejudices, and misconceptions that when internalized can harm one's self-esteem and prevent one from obtaining therapy serve as the operationalization of stigma (Kim et al., 2011). In the study of Tanielian et al. (2016), it was noted that patients and medical professionals agreed that army leaders' attitudes regarding asking for help, particularly those that support it and encourage the "tough it out" mentality, were a substantial obstacle for soldiers in need of or demanding assistance. The narratives and the literature gathered was further confirmed by Russel (2013) where stigma surrounding treatment seeking in the military is a significant problem and less than half of those identified with health conditions seek out help, primarily due to concerns about stigma, how their units and leaders will treat them once they learn that they have an existing condition or dysfunction. Stigma around treatment seeking in the military is a serious problem.

Lack of appropriate equipment was topmost answer of MIU as to facility-based challenges in utilization of treatment. They mentioned that there are available doctors, but the satellite facilities have dearth in necessary equipment to address their problems. Basu et al. (2012) elaborated that there is an existing "infrastructure inequality trap" between public and private treatment sources where private facilities have the greater means to invest in infrastructure therefore having a more "absorptive capacity" to patients, while public sources are plagued by inadequate supplies and poor equipment, of substandard quality. In a similar study by Burnham et al. (2011), customers get the impression that medical staff in public facilities are under pressure, occasionally lacking in medications and functional equipment to manage health issues.

Another important subtheme that emerged from facility-based challenges is the judgment of military doctors upon treatment utilization. Narratives of the MIU stated that they will be looked upon by military doctors as weak and does not know how to take care of himself, including additional risk of disclosure to fellow members of the military. Interestingly, receiving urgently required medical care is directly impacted by prejudice and discrimination in some military organizations (Guilfoyle et al., 2008). It was also indicated that having experienced negative stereotyping or prejudice from health care providers were less likely to seek care when sick. They were unlikely to be happy with the treatment they received and to follow a doctor's advice on how to proceed with treatment (Bogart et al., 2004).

Occupational based challenges were also mentioned by the MIU. It was noted that military men do not have the luxury of time to have their consultation because of their loaded work schedules. Due to their preference to seek treatment at public sources, time constraint has been a major challenge for them due to absence at work and economic loss. The results of the narrative agreed with the study of Green (2014) where *"the time that it took to see clinicians was a barrier and given the commitment patients made to make the visit, participants wished their clinicians to spend more time with them during appointments. Some participants reported that the time and hassle associated with visiting the clinician was problematic, especially when it required time off from work."* Tanielian et al. (2016) further explained that *"care is such that appointments are offered only during duty hours, requiring that service members obtain permission from their*

supervisors or commanders to be absent from work in order to attend the appointment. As a result, their health care is subject to the varying knowledge, beliefs, and will of their commanders violating their request of non-disclosure.” MIU reported that obtaining permission to leave work and go to appointments can be difficult, and many people worried that doing so might have a negative impact on their careers.

With all these challenges, it is timely and imperative to seek out original approaches in treatment delivery for sexual dysfunction. It is recommended to apply technology driven treatment choices which would ensure anonymity and ease of access as to time and convenience. Technology based driven health care was advocated for sensitive medical conditions requiring confidentiality, anonymity, and discreetness. Moreover, technology driven treatment was found out to save time among health professionals and users to save time and money normally spent to travel geographically to a treatment center which would address concerns of MIU as to challenges of treatment utilization.

Treatment delivery for sexual dysfunction would particularly benefit from Telemedicine / Digi-medicine which would answer the complexity of treatment for sexual dysfunction. This system is devoid of stigmatization, which could be accessed anytime, anywhere at the MIU’s own convenient time. This would assure more effective treatment monitoring and success.

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